

CENTRO DE INVESTIGACIONES
DE TRABAJO SOCIAL

ISSN 2244-808X
DL pp 201002Z43506

PERSPECTIVA ACCIÓN Y

Revista de Trabajo Social

Vol. 15 No. 2
Abril - Junio
2025

Universidad del Zulia

Facultad de Ciencias Jurídicas y Políticas
Centro de Investigaciones en Trabajo Social

La influencia de las características interculturales y psicológicas de los participantes en la negociación en el estilo de comunicación y la toma de decisiones (estudios de casos de procesos de negociación)

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Resumen. El artículo profundiza en la persistente presencia e influencia de las características psicológicas interculturales y su efecto en la negociación intercultural. Las relaciones interpersonales y la confianza desempeñan un papel crucial en las negociaciones interculturales. El nivel de confianza, compenetración y respeto dentro de una negociación está muy influido por los antecedentes culturales, lo que a su vez afecta a la disposición a hacer concesiones y encontrar soluciones mutuamente beneficiosas. El objetivo es establecer los mecanismos de evaluación de las características psicológicas interculturales de la negociación dentro del contexto prospectivo oriental. Los métodos analíticos, metódico y de clasificación sirvieron de base a la investigación y permitieron alcanzar el objetivo especificado. Los resultados incluyen las estrategias formuladas para una comunicación eficaz utilizando características psicológicas en el contexto de la negociación intercultural y un conjunto de estudios de casos de características psicológicas de las negociaciones. Las futuras investigaciones sobre el

tema podrían centrarse en determinar los escenarios de las características psicológicas interculturales de la negociación en el contexto prospectivo oriental y en la creación de nuevos modelos interculturales de cooperación con los países del Este.

Palabras clave: comunicación intercultural, características psicológicas, negociación, contexto oriental, comunicación de alto contexto.

The influence of intercultural and psychological features of negotiation participants on communication style and decision-making (case studies of negotiation processes)

Abstract. The article delves into the persistent presence and influence of intercultural psychological characteristics and their effect on intercultural negotiation. Interpersonal relationships and trust play a crucial role in cross-cultural negotiations. The level of trust, rapport and respect within a negotiation is strongly influenced by cultural background, which in turn affects the willingness to make concessions and find mutually beneficial solutions. The objective is to establish the mechanisms for evaluating the intercultural psychological characteristics of negotiation within the prospective Eastern context. Analytical, methodical and classification methods served as the basis for the research and made it possible to achieve the specified objective. The results include strategies formulated for effective communication using psychological characteristics in the context of cross-cultural negotiation and a set of case studies of psychological characteristics of negotiations. Future research on the subject could focus on determining the scenarios of the intercultural psychological characteristics of negotiation in the prospective Eastern context and on the creation of new intercultural models of cooperation with Eastern countries.

Key words: intercultural communication, psychological features, negotiation, Eastern context, high-context communication.

INTRODUCTION

The process of negotiation requires comprehension and management of psychological distinctions and dynamics that emerge when individuals from diverse cultures interact. Previous research in the field of intercultural psychological features is concerned with cultural diversity's effects on negotiation procedures and findings, aiming to determine how differences in cultural norms, values, and cognitive perspectives affect negotiation behaviour and results. This study aims not only to compare and contrast psychological characteristics, behaviours, and attitudes across various cultures in order to comprehend both the differences and similarities of human psychology in an intercultural context, but also to explore the impact of cultural factors on individual and collective psychological processes, examining how cultural values, norms, and practices shape the development of psychological traits and influence cognitive and emotional processes across diverse cultural contexts and designing the mechanisms of cooperation with the Eastern countries. By doing so, it aims to foster greater understanding and empathy between people from different cultural backgrounds.

The architecture of intercultural negotiation could be presented as shown at Picture 1.

In the conditions of the new digital paradigm, which largely determines the life orbit of young generations, it is necessary and important to study the whole range of online activity practices of young people (Eflova et al., 2023). The search for an answer to the question of what practical actions should be taken in order to strengthen the role of the digital environment in the formation of positive behavioral practices of young people and to neutralize and exclude the formation of their negative forms is relevant. In this regard, it is relevant to study the dynamics of changes in the digital behavioral trends of young people and identify their main directions.

In line with the main aim, this paper has the following objectives: to analyse the phenomenon of intercultural negotiation; to understand how cultural peculiarities are influencing negotiation styles; to apply theory-based psychological frameworks to real-life intercultural negotiation scenarios; to develop psychological strategies for effective negotiation in culturally diverse settings.

In «Results» section the authors explore the complexities and nuances of negotiating across different cultures, shedding light on the various cultural factors that come into play. From communication styles to decision-making processes and the impact of values and traditions, we will delve into the key considerations for effectively navigating intercultural negotiations. This section aims to establish a comprehensive theoretical groundwork for the discourse around psychological features of negotiation, illustrating how they form, persist, and complicate intercultural dialogue.

In the «Discussion» section, the paper transitions to proposing practical suggestions and strategies on the consideration of intercultural psychological features of negotiation. A dedicated case study offers empirical data and real-world insights, serving as a critical reflective tool for understanding the multi-faceted nature of intercultural psychological features of negotiation.

METHODS

Firstly, *the analytical method* will be used, which involves the analysis of existing research articles, books, journals and other sources in order to gain a clear understanding of the research topic, as well as knowledge of the main theoretical approaches and concepts related to the topic. Furthermore, the investigation employs a *methodical approach* to compare and contrast different cultural negotiation styles, approaches, and values to identify commonalities and differences. Additionally, a *classification method* will be implemented to systematically organise and structure diverse variations of psychological features, providing insight into their nature, origins, and mechanisms of operation. The practical element of the programme predominantly utilises *case study* methodology, facilitating

examination of genuine interethnic conflict examples and intercultural negotiation issues. This approach skilfully demonstrates the impact of intercultural aspect of psychology in negotiation across diverse sectors and presents pragmatic suggestions to alleviate such partialities, underpinned by detailed explanations of the suggested strategies.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The peculiarities of intercultural communication. In order to grasp the notion of psychological features of this aspect fully, it is imperative to begin with intercultural negotiation and emphasise its critical characteristics. Negotiation is a crucial form of interpersonal interaction in any context since it enables individuals to manage conflict and accomplish their objectives. Despite the universal interest in studying negotiation, there has been an emphasis on investigating the cognitive and rational facets of the negotiation process, with little attention paid to its emotional aspects. However, in recent years, there has been an increasing recognition that emotions have a significant impact on negotiations. As a result, studying emotions in negotiations has gained popularity among academics and researchers.

Referring to the work on the social psychology of negotiation, which was written by J. Z. Rubin & B. R. Brown in 1975 (1975, pp. 110-150) subsequent criteria are the main ones in order for the situation to be a negotiation: the presence of two or more people; the presence of a conflict of interest; the negotiators are voluntarily involved in the conversation; these connections affect the search for a conclusion and resolution of the situation regarding a specific issue between people, as well as the interchange of existing knowledge of the participants; the requirements for negotiation, which are presented by each of the parties, also play a key role in finding mutual understanding and final agreement. In the publication, the authors introduced the term “intercultural negotiation” and stated that negotiations are the best option to resolve the conflict. This article also presents a valuable contribution of other scientists who fully help to understand the problem of comprehending intercultural negotiations, for example, in the article of Interpersonal Relations of S. S. Komorita & C. D. Parks (1995, pp. 183–207), the writers identify several types of negotiations – conflict management or transactional negotiations. Interactions and disputes can range from basic daily encounters and misunderstandings to intricate organizational predicaments, legal conflicts or even those significant enough to instigate wars. They can occur between only two individuals debating one topic, or they may encompass multiple subject matters, various parties or numerous individuals speaking on behalf of a particular constituency. They can be brief or enduring and can transpire via virtual or in-person communication. Regardless of the nature of negotiations, they all share a common aim: for the involved parties to collaborate in order to prevent a deadlock and achieve a mutual agreement, while also striving to compete to attain the best possible outcome.

All these subtleties are very important for the negotiation process. L. Thompson (1990, pp. 515–532) in his work about negotiation and behavior and D. Pruitt, & J. Rubin in the article about social conflicts (1986, pp. 86-97), immersed in the issue of the structure of negotiations. The process depends on the degree of conflict that exists between parties’ interests. Pure conflict, also known as fixed-sum or win-lose or value claiming or purely distributive bargaining, refers to situations where parties’ interests are conflicting and perfectly negatively correlated and thus bargainers’ primary motivation is to maximize their utility or their share of fixed-sum payoffs. At the opposite end, there are pure coordination situations that describe negotiations where bargainers’ interests are very compatible.

Regarding the issue of the outcome of the negotiations, L. Thompson highlighted several standard situations. Integrative negotiation agreement is considered efficient and Pareto (1935) optimal if it fulfills the requirements of all participating parties without causing any harm to them and if there are no better alternatives that could serve the interests of one or both parties. Speaking about the distributive negotiation agreement, it refers to the process by which individuals decide how to distribute resources and can be better comprehended via the traditional ultimatum game. This is an experiment in which the proposer, a player, is presented with a fixed sum of money and has the chance to divide it with another player, the responder, who can either accept or reject the offer if it is deemed unfair. In the first scenario, neither player receives any payment. However, if the responder agrees to the proposal, the sum of money is distributed based on the proposal, and the distributive aspect of the bargaining process indicates the percentage of the initial amount that each negotiator will receive. Negotiations can lead to economic and socio-psychological outcomes. Socio-psychological results from negotiations include negotiators' satisfaction and the relationship between parties, as well as their willingness to engage in future negotiations with the same opponent. The subjective value (Curhan, 2007) of negotiators is one of the most commonly researched socio-psychological outcomes of negotiations.

Some academic disciplines, including sociology, cognitive psychology, and political science, have significantly influenced the study of negotiations. This has resulted in the consensus that this field is one of the most challenging. The work of D. Druckman (1977), which is related to the topic of social-psychological perspectives, depicts that negotiation process primarily centers on two research areas: a) differences among negotiators in terms of individual factors such as demographics (e.g. gender) and personality traits, and b) coincidental characteristics (e.g. power). While gender remains a topic of controversy, with conflicting evidence on its impact, culture has emerged as a more substantial element. Women frequently encounter challenges due to societal expectations, facing a predicament between conforming to gender stereotypes and adopting a more effective, assertive approach. Backlash effects and societal pressure complicate negotiators' strategies. However, studies suggest that gender may not have a significant impact on negotiation competitiveness. Limited insight has been found in predicting negotiator performance through individual characteristics, including cognitive abilities, which have also been questioned regarding their practical implications. Cultural differences have been identified as having a more prominent effect on negotiation outcomes. Acknowledging and understanding such differences can enable negotiators to develop appropriate strategies. Thus, whilst individual differences may not strongly predict bargaining performance, cultural nuances are deemed to play a significant role in negotiations. Regarding contextual features, social psychological research examined these factors in negotiation, including communication, payoffs, deadlines, and negotiator power. Power, sourced from coercive, reward, legitimate, expert, and referent power were central topics. The Best Alternative to a Negotiated Agreement (BATNA) was viewed as a primary source of power, affecting negotiators' reliance on opponents and their success in achieving desired outcomes. As negotiation research decreased in the late 1970s as a result of the social cognitive movement, scholars from management schools began to utilize behavioural decision research (BDR) to inform negotiation theory. The emphasis was on the significance of decision-making in circumstances that are outside the control of negotiators.

Thus, the evidence suggests that positive emotions offer various advantages to the participants of transactions, whereas negative or neutral feelings generally result in significant negative outcomes. However, the current study uncovers inconsistencies within the conclusions, explicable

by the topic's complexity and the multitude of relevant factors. Moreover, the investigation of emotions in negotiations remains nascent, necessitating further research. The growing fascination with emotional dynamics in negotiations in recent times possibly links to the emergence of positive psychology as a new field of study within psychology during this period. Positive psychology, which conducts scientific research on positive emotions, has aided comprehension of how positivity can enhance outcomes across various aspects of life.

Recent research has investigated the questions of predictability and anxiety on willingness to interact with a person from another cultural group (Logan et al., 2017). This research group argues upon the fact that Asian people are more apt to seek psychological support (authoritative people, colleagues, friends, religious community) while involved in intercultural negotiation. Such characteristics as higher anxiety, uncertainty, ethnocentrism and help-seeking are more applicable to Asian people due to the peculiarities of their acculturation.

Asian negotiators prefer to save face and ignore conflicts as well as use tactics leading to desired outcomes that meet the interests of the collective. The negotiating parties may start their communication with two different motivations: claiming value and creating value. In this case, negotiation could be regarded as a process of cooperation and competition. Intercultural negotiation within the Eastern context is complex and challenging because of the cultural singularity. M. Benoliel (2013) describes it as unstated, implicit, and internalized in subtle behavioral patterns.

Yu. Long and Q. Lei (2022) discuss the psychological features of Eastern negotiators within the framework of high-context communication. They give a list of these psychological features: group-oriented values of communication, mutual-face concern, spiral logic, indirect style of negotiation, status-oriented style, self-effacement style, listener-oriented style, context-based understanding (Long & Lei, 2022).

Psychological Features in Intercultural Negotiation

Psychology has a crucial function in intercultural negotiation, as it involves comprehending diverse cultural values, communication styles, and views on power and hierarchy. These aspects have a direct impact on the negotiation dynamics and can considerably affect the outcomes. Thus, it is essential to grasp psychological underpinnings of intercultural negotiation for successful cross-cultural interactions.

Negotiation arises from the dynamics of social interaction, making theoretical frameworks focused on the social aspect crucial when analysing how emotions are involved in negotiation. Psychosocial theories, for instance R.S. Lazarus's (1991), provide valuable insight into the intricate linkages between emotions, cognition, and social exchange, by clarifying how emotions influence interaction and affect people's understanding and evaluation of social encounters. Moreover, these theories highlight the emergence of emotions as a consequence of social interactions. Social constructivist models, endorsed by scholars such as J. R. Averill (1980), operate under the assumption that emotions are best understood within the context of the social environment, surpassing the idea of emotions as mere psychological responses. Instead, emotions are perceived as interpretive constructs that are influenced by culture, language, and social learning. They serve as a means for individuals to derive meaning from their social environment.

E. J. Lawler and J. Yoon (1995) proposed that affective commitment to a relationship is formed through the emotional implications of repeated negotiations between the same parties. Based on

the assumption that interdependence fosters a need for recurrent negotiations, Lawler and Yoon argued that frequent agreements between the same parties generate mild positive emotions, which leads to the establishment of dyadic relationships. Negotiators start to attribute their feelings of control and associated positive emotions, partly to their relationship following Lawler and Yoon's expression (p. 155). The process ultimately leads to the establishment of affective commitment, creating the basis for subsequent interactions. Additionally, B. Barry & R. L. Oliver (1996) offered a broader perspective, highlighting the emotional states that carry importance at different stages of a negotiation encounter. Firstly, the authors identified anticipatory emotional states, suggesting that they arise from the bargaining environment, past interactions within the dyad, and the negotiators' dispositional affect. Secondly, they argued that the emotions experienced during negotiations stem from initial offers, concessions, and other tactical behaviours, which lead to adjustments in aspirations and expectations and thus influence tactical conduct. Lastly, the model investigates the impact of post-negotiation affect resulting from particular bargaining outcomes and how parties attribute those outcomes. Post-negotiation affect is believed to influence future interaction and subsequent behaviour, including the parties' efficiency in implementing the negotiated settlement.

Overall, the majority of the reviewed conceptual works present formal models that can be tested empirically through specific predictions. Though all of these models acknowledge that emotion is an outcome of bargaining, only one places significant emphasis on it. The remaining models emphasise the unfolding of emotions or their strategic regulation within the encounter. Together, these models do not directly compete with each other, but instead provide complementary frameworks that tackle different aspects of the negotiation process from various perspectives.

Approaches that focus on the social aspects of emotion are vital in understanding the impact of emotions on negotiation. Our perspective is that these approaches are interconnected with the study of individual differences, as opposed to being separate from it. Research further demonstrates that differences in people's motivational tendencies significantly affect how mood influences the cognitive aspects of negotiation. A thorough comprehension of the function of emotions in negotiations necessitates an assessment of the variations in emotional experiences and expressions during continuous social interactions among individuals. Several stable individual difference variables that have been associated with emotional experience or expression are of potential relevance for analysing emotions in negotiations. These individual differences comprise emotional expressivity, self-monitoring, and the "Big Five" personality dimensions (McCrae & John, 1992); the relatively new field of emotional intelligence; and gender-related emotional differentiation. *Emotional expressivity* is frequently conceptualized as a consistent dispositional trait that comprises multiple facets, including impulse strength, negative expressivity, positive expressivity, expressive confidence, and emotion masking. These facets are associated with positive and negative emotions and several of the Big Five personality dimensions investigated the circumstances in which emotional experience is reflected in emotional expression. Their study indicated that highly expressive individuals exhibit expression for both positive and negative emotions, whereas low-expressivity individuals only express positive emotional experiences. The dispositional trait of *self-monitoring* offers additional insight into the function of emotional expression in negotiation. People with high self-monitoring show greater proficiency in communicating emotions, both verbally and through facial expressions, than those with low self-monitoring. In a set of studies, R. E. Lucas (2001) discovered that extroverts were inclined towards recollection of positive words and positive judgments, whereas those high in neuroticism demonstrated a greater recollection of negative words and made more negative overall judgments.

The study by Van Kleef, De Dreu, and Manstead (2001) investigated the interpersonal effects of emotions during negotiation and found that participants faced with an angry opponent tended to make lower demands and concede more than those negotiating with a happy or non-emotional opponent. The research conducted by Van Kleef et al. supports the social functions perspective and shows that anger facilitates collaboration, whereas happiness encourages competition. These findings disclose novel understandings of the impact of positive and negative emotions on negotiation outcomes. Antecedently, it was generally accepted that positive emotions increase negotiator efficacy, while negative emotions reduce it. However, this belief was predominantly grounded in the intrapersonal consequences of emotions, whereas Van Kleef and colleagues' study implies the need for a more nuanced understanding. Their investigation into the interpersonal effects of emotions uncovered that negative emotions may prove more advantageous than positive emotions in negotiation situations. Although seemingly paradoxical, this is not invariably the case. Previous research on intrapersonal effects has mainly focused on integrative negotiation tasks, demonstrating the advantages of positive emotions and the disadvantages of negative emotions. However, Van Kleef et al. examined a distributive negotiation task which revealed anger to be more "effective" than happiness. Therefore, it seems that anger is more advantageous when claiming value in distributive negotiations, while happiness may be more beneficial in integrative negotiations.

The significant dependency on simulations of mixed-motive bargaining in negotiation research leads to questioning the portrayal of genuine emotions in the social interactions being analysed. While individuals involved in experimental setups may experience some mild positive and negative emotions, the actual breadth of emotions felt during real negotiations, such as anger, delight, anxiety, and frustration, could be influenced by personal stakes or contextualized social relationships, which cannot be easily replicated in laboratory or classroom scenarios. Real-world negotiations frequently involve substantial interpersonal relationships, high monetary stakes, and life-altering events, among other factors which are hard to recreate in simulated settings. As a result, the generalizability of laboratory studies examining negotiators' emotional state is doubtful, mainly since the range of topics that can be simulated is limited. While experiments and simulations are valuable tools for comprehending information processing during negotiations, they may not wholly encompass the significance of norms, values, morals, emotions, relationships, power structures, and other pivotal factors for understanding conflict and its progression. It is crucial to use a multifaceted approach to gain a thorough understanding of negotiation and conflict processes.

Essential results of the previous studies which draw the relationship between cultural dimensions and psychological features: frequent agreements between the same parties generate mild positive emotions, which lead to the establishment of dyadic relationships; emotions can serve as motivations or hindrances to behavior, controlling social interaction and directing cognitive or behavioral adaptation; positive emotions increase negotiator efficacy, while negative emotions reduce it.

The following psychological features have been identified as general for any type of negotiation process: emotional expressivity; self-monitoring; "Big Five" personality dimensions (McCrae and John, 1992); the relatively new field of emotional intelligence; gender-related emotional differentiation.

Psychological aspect tends to become crucial in intercultural negotiation as it allows taking into consideration certain ethnic tactics of communication, thinking patterns, attitudes to time or risks, preferences in individual or collective behaviour, etc.

Outlining the way to negotiate with Eastern partners, it's necessary to bear in mind that they are known to be masters of negotiation. A lot has been written of how to communicate with Eastern negotiators but the problem lies in the fact that most of the studies were undertaken by representatives of western cultures and the results are presented through western culture lenses.

M. Svetlicic underlines the ambivalent position of Eastern negotiators towards foreigners. In the process of negotiation one may communicate with “the Maoist bureaucrat, Confucian gentlemen and Sun Tzu strategist” at the same time. The collective nature of Asian society is consistent with Asians' broad, contextual view of the world and their belief that events are highly complex and determined by many factors and all these factors are influencing on the process of negotiation (Svetličič, 2022).

The main psychological focus in negotiations with Eastern partners is determined by principles: courtesy and loyalty, harmony, keeping up appearance “no matter what”, humility and respect for age and rank. Relationships are more important and have long-term perspective than the results of momentary interaction.

DISCUSSION

Strategies for effective communication using psychological features in the context of intercultural negotiation

The preceding section examines common forms of psychological features, concentrating on how they emerge in the context of intercultural negotiation. Research has revealed that successful and cooperative negotiators have the following abilities and characteristics (Rubin & Brown, 1975): *controlled risk behaviour, ability to perceive and judge events in their complexity, ambiguity tolerance, and positive self-image, cooperative and nonauthoritarian attitude.*

The function of psychological features in intercultural negotiation is a crucial aspect of effective communication and successful resolution of conflicts. In cross-cultural interactions, individuals bring their unique cultural background, values, and behavior patterns to the negotiation table. Understanding the psychological nuances at play in these interactions can greatly affect the outcome of the negotiation process.

Intercultural negotiation at an academic level entails a multifaceted interaction of psychological factors that affect the dynamics of the negotiation process. A comprehensive understanding of these factors is vital for effectively managing the intricacies of cross-cultural communication and collaboration within an academic context. The negotiation process consists of three phases, which may differ in interpretation and approach based on cultural disparities.

In this context, several approaches can be suggested. The primary approach is to *Establish Communication and Form a Relationship*. The initial contact and the desire to commence negotiations are pivotal as they serve to lay the groundwork for a careful evaluation of market conditions and the identification of viable negotiation partners. Diverse cultural perspectives meaningfully impact this phase. In Western cultures, selecting appropriate negotiation partners is determined by factors such as competence, cost-effectiveness, and quality. However, in collectivist cultures like those found in various Asian countries, partners may be chosen based on existing mutual obligations, despite the availability of more attractive alternatives. After initial contact has been made, it becomes imperative

for both parties to establish a foundation of mutual trust. This is pivotal for successful negotiations, as the absence of such trust can lead to competition, deception, and manoeuvring. Additionally, differing cultures display a range of trust-building and trust-maintaining behaviours and symbols. In cultures that place a high value on personal relationships (Thomas et al., 1998), including those in Arab countries or Latin America, it can be crucial to establish a connection with the negotiator as an individual, in addition to their corporate role. This may involve engaging in seemingly irrelevant personal conversations, which, whilst not customary in other cultures, can play a central role in building the trust necessary for successful negotiations. Individuals from task-oriented cultures, such as Germany, may find it difficult to navigate initial contact protocols and establish mutual rapport. This is due to the lesser emphasis on interpersonal etiquette in such cultures.

Negotiating and reaching agreements entail several rounds of discussions, encompassing proposing, agreeing or disagreeing, engaging in conversation, and summarizing agreements. The cultural subtleties of presenting proposals and advocating for one's interests, as well as negotiating, and non-verbal communication, are crucial during the process. These cultural factors impact the range between the highest and lowest demands in a negotiation which is essential for reaching an agreement, and also affect the exchange of offers and counteroffers. German negotiators are often perceived as inflexible due to their narrow negotiation range, leading to hitting the pain threshold after just a few negotiation rounds.

To develop a deeper insight into a foreign culture and its inhabitants, *one should pursue in-depth examination and exploration*. This may include submerging oneself within the culture's customs, traditions, language, and history. It is also beneficial to engage in dialogue with members of the culture and to pursue educational resources for further understanding. Additional approaches may involve examining cultural customs and communication styles, as well as exploring the values, beliefs, and societal norms that shape the viewpoint of the given culture.

To create an appropriate negotiating plan, it is imperative to first establish and cultivate relationships with the other culture whilst respecting cultural norms of both parties. This necessitates understanding communication styles, decision-making processes, and rapport-building methods of the other culture. To commence negotiations, we can arrange informal meetings or social events to begin building rapport and trust. We should consider the preferred forms and formats for interaction of the other culture, and aim to comply with their negotiation protocols in a way that is comfortable for all parties involved. After establishing initial relationships, we can proceed to address substantive issues by organizing formal negotiation sessions. These sessions allow for information exchanges and mutual education, ensuring that both parties thoroughly understand each other's perspectives and needs. If the other party adopts a positional approach or makes demands, we can reframe the conversation to encourage an interest-based approach. This involves prioritising underlying interests and shared goals over positions.

It is equally important to analyze and interpret the factors affecting the situation at hand and devise an appropriate response. Upon identifying cultural diversity hindering the advancement of negotiations, strive to comprehend the underlying rationale for their conduct or perspectives. Take advantage of prior investigations and interactions to elucidate the circumstances, establish a theory concerning the reasons and feasible consequences of the opinions, attitudes, and actions displayed. Choose a course of action and devise at least two tactics to contemplate executing when dealing with cross-cultural negotiations.

This section identified some strategies for managing cross-cultural negotiations using psychological features. These techniques are contingent on your willingness or ability to adjust to the other party's culture, as well as their corresponding willingness or ability to adjust to yours. The choices are: *adherence; avoidance and contention; adaptation; adoption; and advancement.*

The aforementioned strategies emphasise the significance of attending to the psychological aspects that pertain to negotiation. Such considerations either facilitate or impede the participants' ability to attain the desired outcome in the form of gaining valuable benefits and experiences.

Therefore, the following tools for strategies can be identified: *controlled risk behaviour, ability to perceive and judge events in their complexity, ambiguity tolerance, positive self-image, cooperative and nonauthoritarian attitude.* Additionally, it is worth mentioning actual strategies that can be often used: *establishing communication and forming a relationship, negotiating and reaching agreements, pursuing in-depth examination and exploration in cultures and traditions and creating an appropriate negotiating plan.*

For instance, Chinese style of negotiation displays collective spirit and demonstrates very polite and indirect communication strategy. Flattering and ambiguous expressions are considered normal in the process of negotiation. The Chinese don't rely on words; their sentences are short meanwhile they pay more attention to posture, expression and tone of voice. The Chinese avoid saying "No" at all costs because it could insult the other party, or embarrass someone. At the same time, "Yes" could mean disagreement. It is recommended to ask the same questions several times while negotiating with the Chinese so that to fix on the real point. During negotiation be ready to talk simultaneously on different issues and in a chaotic manner. One may use such tools as smile or silence bringing them ahead as welcoming techniques to come to terms with the Chinese partners. For Chinese negotiator silence is time for reflection. Showing sincere respect and interest for local Chinese culture will help one avoid mistakes in negotiation (Svetličič, 2022).

Case study of psychological features of negotiations

The case section of the paper serves as a critical component in applying theoretical knowledge to real-world situations. This segment provides students with the opportunity to analyse and evaluate complex scenarios, often rooted in authentic business, legal, or ethical dilemmas. Through the examination of these cases, students can develop practical problem-solving skills, enhance their critical thinking abilities, and gain valuable insights into the application of course concepts in various professional contexts. Each case study is situated within a distinct context: educational establishments, corporate settings.

Case Study No. 1 illustrates the differences in cultural characteristics, due to which employees who have just got a job in another country may suffer because of the psychological features of doing business and negotiations. Thus, negotiation is a crucial global strategy. Leaders who fail to follow intercultural psychological negotiation styles and strategies experience difficulty in establishing rapport with their employees and management. This challenge is more prevalent for relocated workers. Active listening, open communication, trust building and demonstrating respect are essential elements of building a relationship. They indicate that you appreciate their input and are interested in hearing what they have to say. Thus, the strategy of *establishing communication and forming a relationship* is applicable in the 1st case. In summary, effective communication, empathy, trust, and respect are fundamental aspects of building and maintaining robust relationships.

Case Study No. 2 is about negotiators who belong to high power distance cultures and tend to adhere to hierarchical decision-making structures, while their counterparts from low power distance cultures may pursue more egalitarian approaches. Consequently, this could potentially result in various misunderstandings, conflicts and, ultimately, failed negotiations. The case illustrates the challenges and importance of intercultural negotiation dynamics in the tourism industry. However, the strategy of *pursuing in-depth examination and exploration in cultures and traditions of another country* is vital to reach an agreement or find a compromise. This strategy includes: cultural immersion pre-supposing spending a significant amount of time living and interacting with the local population to gain a deep understanding of their customs, traditions, and way of life.

Case Study No. 1. The role of culture in intercultural psychological negotiating styles using the strategy of establishing communication and forming a relationship

General problem formulation. The global conditions of negotiation can also be characterized as a global strategy – one that is foundational. Observations show that leaders who do not follow intercultural psychological negotiating styles and strategies are unable to establish a connection with their subordinates and management. This problem is particularly noticeable among employees who have been transferred from one country to another. Questions arise as to the importance of similar cultural features in the workplace, the possibility of working in a foreign country without changing one's habits and traditions, and how different the psychological negotiating styles are in different countries.

Key task. Propose possible ways to address the cultural and habit differences of employees based on psychological factors.

Context for solving the task. Paulo works in an international firm and was recently transferred from Italy to Japan, which was quite a stressful situation for him. Italy represents a polychronic culture, where people live by polychronic time, juggle multiple tasks simultaneously, and cannot adhere to a schedule. Conversely, Japan is a country with a monochronic culture. The Japanese work diligently and meticulously fulfil their duties. After living for so many years in a country where interpersonal human relationships play a significant role, and communication with people is more important than an accepted plan of action, Paulo was extremely surprised to find that in Japan, being late and leaving work early is prohibited. Unfortunately, this led to mental problems for him as he struggled to find like-minded individuals and close friends, feeling completely alone in a foreign country. This state led to emotional burnout and a lack of motivation to work.

Tasks that could lead to a solution.

- 1) To determine which strategies and action plans will help to adapt quickly and understand a different mentality.
- 2) To develop an additional sense of understanding that another person has grown up in a different environment, has different habits, and may not understand our intentions or expectations.
- 3) To conduct a thorough analysis and study the rules that exist in Japan.
- 4) To forecast the possible outcomes if the chosen recommendations are followed, and how this will help find the best solution.
- 5) To conduct a survey among local residents, employees, and colleagues who can help in the difficult situation of adapting to foreign traditions.

The purpose of this case is to consider the difficulties that workers may encounter when operating in foreign nations due to cultural and habitual disparities, particularly emphasising the psychological aspects of negotiation styles. The specific scenario concerns an individual named Paulo, who experienced a significant amount of stress and mental health problems due to disparities between Italian and Japanese cultures after being transferred to work in Japan. The aim of the first case is to propose possible ways to address these cultural and habit differences of employees based on psychological factors. To efficiently adjust to a different mind-set, it is vital to comprehend and implement appropriate measures such as empathy and awareness towards individuals with diverse cultural backgrounds, conducting meticulous evaluations of the regulations in the host nation, prediction of the potential impacts of the preferred suggestions, and gathering feedback from neighbours, colleagues, and staff to facilitate the adaptation to foreign traditions.

Case Study No. 2: Cross-cultural negotiations: the impact of power distance on decision making using the strategy of pursuing in-depth examination and exploration in cultures and traditions of another country

General Problem Formulation: In the global business landscape, the nuances of cross-cultural negotiations become crucial for successful partnerships and collaborations. One of the central challenges is the varying power distance among different cultures and how it affects decision-making processes. It is observed that negotiators from high power distance cultures tend to follow hierarchical decision-making structures, while those from low power distance cultures may adopt more egalitarian approaches. This can lead to misunderstandings, conflicts, and failed negotiations.

Key Task: Explore the influence of power distance on negotiation styles and develop strategies to effectively bridge the gap in decision making.

Context for Solving the Task: Maria, an executive from Brazil, is leading negotiations with a team from Sweden. Brazil is known for its high power distance culture where individuals expect clear hierarchies and centralized decision-making, while Sweden embodies low power distance, promoting more democratic and inclusive decision-making processes. As a result, the negotiation process becomes strained due to conflicting approaches to reaching consensus, leading to potential breakdowns in the partnership.

Tasks Leading to a Solution:

- 1) To analyze the cultural dimensions and their impact on decision-making styles in Brazil and Sweden.
- 2) To conduct a comparative analysis of negotiation strategies employed in high and low power distance cultures.
- 3) To develop a negotiation framework that accommodates both hierarchical and egalitarian decision-making preferences.
- 4) To implement cross-cultural training for the negotiation teams to raise awareness and bridge the understanding gap.
- 5) To assess the potential benefits and challenges of integrating diverse decision-making approaches and strategize for a mutually acceptable negotiation process.

The aim of the second case is to tackle the difficulties that arise from different cultures' varying power distance and its influence on decision-making in cross-cultural negotiations. The defined ob-

jectives entail gaining comprehension of the cultural dimensions in Brazil and Sweden, performing a comparative analysis of negotiation methods in high and low power distance cultures, creating a negotiation framework that caters to hierarchical and egalitarian decision-making preferences, instituting cross-cultural training to bridge the knowledge divide, and evaluating the advantages and obstacles of incorporating several decision-making approaches to reach an agreement. Additionally, speaking about other possible strategies, *Negotiation Framework Development* used to develop a negotiation framework that accommodates both hierarchical and egalitarian decision-making preferences is crucial. This framework should outline a flexible approach that acknowledges and respects the different cultural tendencies while aiming to achieve consensus and mutual understanding.

Overall, these two cases show us what the intercultural aspect is from the practical point of view. When comparing both of them, it is evident that the negotiation strategies employed have a significant influence on the outcome, whether positive or negative.

Negotiations with Eastern partners are long-term oriented and considered to be an investment of time and energy in relationship-building. Speed is thought to be impolite, dangerous and cunning in interactions; it creates chaos and a mess. Eastern partners prefer to reach agreements at the very last moment of a negotiation or even after a deadline.

As a result of the study presented in this paper, two possible negotiation scenarios with Eastern partners could be given (Table 1).

TABLE 1. Possible negotiation scenarios with Eastern partners

Negotiation scenario	Strategy used in negotiation	What does it mean?
trust is high and a 'win-win approach' to the negotiations is displayed	a cooperation strategy is used	they expect and seek long-term relationships
trust is low and a 'win-lose approach' is adopted, stratagems are relevant (negotiators resort to rites and rituals as a tactics)	a competitive strategy is used	they do everything to win and use the context, situation and time; they are ready to negotiate on their terms

Thus, intercultural negotiations in Eastern tradition are quite complicated, complex and demanding. They tend to progress slowly, step by step, and build mutual trust between negotiators. Once one decides to come to terms with their Eastern partners, they should not expect the result overnight.

CONCLUSION

A comprehensive understanding of intercultural psychological features in negotiations and how to navigate them effectively necessitates a meticulous analysis of the pertinent theoretical underpinnings and the adoption of detailed strategies aimed at addressing biases in diverse cultural settings. To explore this subject, specific cases were selected to illustrate the most pivotal challenges associated with intercultural negotiation dynamics. Subsequently, the theoretical framework of research on intercultural psychology in the context of negotiation was utilized to elucidate the scenarios depicted in these cases.

Figure 1. Challenges and opportunities for the development of multicultural education

The research aimed at analysing psychological characteristics, behaviours, and attitudes across various cultures to establish the similarities and differences of human psychology in an intercultural context allowed to study the impact of cultural factors on individual and collective psychological processes through the assessment of the influence of cultural values, norms, and practices on the development of psychological traits and cognitive and emotional processes across diverse cultural contexts.

The analysis led to the determination of the mechanisms of interaction with the Eastern countries. The application of such mechanisms promotes better understanding and empathy between people from different cultural backgrounds.

BIBLIOGRAPHIC REFERENCES

- Averill, J. R. (1985). *A constructivist view of emotion*. In Springer series in social psychology (pp. 305–309). Springer.
- Barry, B., & Oliver, R. L. (1996). Affect in dyadic negotiation: A model and propositions. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 67(2), 127–143.
- Benoliel, M. (2013). Negotiating successfully in Asia. *Eurasian Journal of Social Sciences*, 1(1), 1-18.
- Curhan, J. R. (2007). “What do people value when they negotiate?”. *Massachusetts Institute of Technology*, 55–87.
- Druckman, D. (1977). *Negotiations: Social-psychological perspectives*. Beverly Hills, CA: Sage, pp. 87-95.
- Gulbro, R. D., & Herbig, P. (1999). Cultural characteristics and negotiation styles. *Emerald Group Publishing Limited*, 47–53(7).

- Haas, S. M., & Stafford, L. (1998). Relationship maintenance behaviors in couples. *American Psychological Association*, 75–87.
- Hofstede, G., Hofstede, G. J., & Minkov, M. (1991). *Cultures and organizations: Software of the mind*. McGraw-Hill eBooks, pp. 27-47.
- Janosik, R. J. (1987). Rethinking the culture-negotiation. *Negotiation Journal*, 385–395.
- Komorita, S. S., & Parks, C. D. (1995). Interpersonal relations: Mixed-motive interaction. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 183–207.
- Larrick, R. P., & Blount, S. (1997). The claiming effect: Why players are more generous in social dilemmas than in ultimatum games. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 810–825.
- Lawler, E. J., & Yoon, J. (1995). Structural power and emotional processes in negotiation: A social exchange approach. *Cornell University ILR School*, 154–175.
- Lazarus, R. S. (1991). Emotion and adaptation. *Oxford University Press*, 87–94.
- Logan, S., Steel, Z., & Hunt, C. (2017). Ethnic status and engagement with health services: Attitudes toward help-seeking and intercultural willingness to interact among South East Asian students in Australia. *Transcultural Psychiatry*, 54, 192-210.
- Long, Y., & Lei, Q. (2022). Cultural differences between China and America in the international negotiations under the cultural dimensions. *Studies in Linguistics and Literature*, 6(3), 81-91. <https://doi.org/10.22158/sll.v6n3p81>
- Lucas, R. E., & Diener, E. (2001). International encyclopedia of the social & behavioral sciences. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 81, 343–356.
- McCrae, R. R., & John, O. P. (1992). An introduction to the five-factor model and its applications. *Journal of Personality*, 60(2), 175–215.
- Pareto, V. (1935). *The mind and society: A treatise on general sociology*. Harcourt Brace, pp. 237-262.
- Pruitt, D., & Rubin, J. (1986). *Social conflict: Escalation, stalemate, and settlement*. Random House, pp. 86-97.
- Ross, L., & Ward, A. (1995). *Psychological barriers to dispute resolution*. In M. P. Zanna (Ed.), *Advances in experimental social psychology* (pp. 255–304). Academic Press.
- Rubin, J. Z., & Brown, B. R. (1975). The social psychology of bargaining and negotiation. *Academic Press*, 259–288.
- Svetličič, M. (2022). How to negotiate with the Chinese? *Journal of Innovative Business and Management = Mednarodno Inovativno Poslovanje*, 14(1), 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.32015/JIBM.2022.14.1.5>
- Thompson, L. (1990). Negotiation behavior and outcomes: Empirical evidence and theoretical issues. *Psychological Bulletin*, 515–532.
- Van Kleef, G. A., De Dreu, C. K. W., & Manstead, A. S. R. (2004). The interpersonal effects of anger and happiness in negotiations. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 86(1), 57–76.